

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL FOR

Unraveling the time evolution and *post mortem* changes of nanometric MnOOH during *in situ* chemical oxidation of
ciprofloxacin by activated PMS

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Text SM-1

UHPLC chromatographic conditions for the CIP oxidation byproducts

The samples were analyzed using an Agilent 1290 Infinity II Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatograph (UHPLC - Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Chromatographic separation was performed on a C18 column (50 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 μm, Zorbax Eclipse Plus, Agilent, USA). The mobile phase of the UHPLC consisted of 0.1% formic acid (solvent A) and MeOH (solvent B). The chromatographic gradient used was as follows: 0-20 min, 65% B; 20-24 min, 65 to 85% B; 24-27 min, 85-65% B. Column oven and autosampler temperatures were set to 30°C. The liquid flow and injection volume were 0.25 mL min⁻¹ and 2.0 μL, respectively.

q-TOF/MS analyses

Quantitative analyte analyses were performed using an Agilent 6545 Q-TOF/MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an ESI Jet interface in positive ion mode and capillary voltage of 4.0 kV. The desolvation gas flow was 11 L min⁻¹ and the gas flow in the cone was 8 L min⁻¹. The low and high collision energies were 6 V and 12~17 V, respectively. Molecular ion and fragment ions were simultaneously obtained by the MS^E acquisition mode. Data collected were analyzed over a range of 100 to 1000 Da and processed by the MassHunter Workstation Software version B.08.00.

Analysis of CIP degradation products by UHPL-qTOF/MS

The q-TOF-MS/MS analyses were carried out in the MS fullscan and MS^E modes to obtain information about the exact masses of the CIP standard and possible degradation products. For the samples analysis, a 10 mg L⁻¹ solution was diluted in H₂O. The total ion chromatograms (TIC) of samples in the ESI⁺ positive ionization mode showed peaks of ion intensities corresponding to the degradation products of ciprofloxacin (CIP). The spectrometric parameters were optimized for the CIP standard. For the identification of degradation products, parameters were tested at low and high collision energies.

Text SM-2

Experimental details for elucidating working oxidants

The use of DMPO and TEMP as spin probe were carried out using 5 mL of deionized H₂O (pH 3). In a typical experiment, 5 mg of MnOOH and 5 mg of PMS (corresponding to 1.0 g L⁻¹ of each compound) were transferred to a 20 mL glass flask. Then, acidified H₂O (5 mL – pH 3) were added to start the reaction under magnetic stirring. After a 1 min reaction, 125 μL of a 4 mol L⁻¹ DMPO (final concentration of 100 mmol L⁻¹) solution was added and the reaction was let for 1 min under stirring. After this time, to a 1 mL of sample, NaOH solution (60 μL of a 0.125 mol L⁻¹) was added to precipitate Mn(II) ions (pH ~7). Then, the samples were centrifuged for 30 s to separate the solid MnOOH. For ESR analyses, 200 μL of samples was transferred to a quartz capillary tube. The same procedure was used for the UHPLC analyses - see below the analysis's details.

For the experiment using TEMP (50 mmol L⁻¹), only ESR measurements were carried out.

UHPLC chromatographic conditions for the DMPO oxidation byproducts

The oxidation products resulting from DMPO oxidation by unknown radicals were carried out by UHPLC using a C18 column (50 mm × 2.1 mm i.d., 1.8 μm, Zorbax Eclipse Plus, Agilent, USA) column and a mixture of 0.1% formic acid (solvent A) and ACN (solvent B) as the stationary and mobile phase, respectively. A gradient elution mode at 0.35 mL min⁻¹ was used to separate the main products according to the following sequence: 0-1 min, 5% B; 1-10 min, 95% B; 10-10.1 min, 95-5% B; and 10.5-13 min, 5% B. The injection volume and column temperature (including the autosampler) were 1.0 μL and 35 °C.

q-TOF/MS analyses

Quantitative analyte analyses were performed using an Agilent 6545 Q-TOF/MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with an ESI Jet interface in positive ion mode and capillary voltage of 2.0 kV. The desolvation gas flow and gas flow in the cone were 11,0 L min⁻¹ and 10 L min⁻¹, respectively. The collision energies ranged from 5 V to 16 V. Other variables such as source temperature, fragmentation voltage, skimmer voltage, and nozzle voltage were set to 300 °C, 40 V,

35 V and 225 V, respectively. Molecular and fragment ions were simultaneously obtained by the MS^E acquisition mode. Data collected were analyzed over a range from 50 to 600 Da and processed by the MassHunter Workstation Software version B.08.00.

Table SM-1 Pseudo-first order kinetic constants (k) for the removal of CIP and TOC at different pH conditions. Experimental conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, and 25 °C. Mean values were obtained after two repetitions.

pH	CIP fraction		TOC 1
	$k_{obs} / 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	R^2	$k_{obs} / 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$

Table SM-2 Pseudo-first order kinetic constants (k) for the removal of CIP and TOC at different PMS concentrations. Reaction conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, pH 3.0, and 25 °C. Mean values were obtained after two repetitions.

[PMS] / g L ⁻¹	CIP fraction		TOC f
	$k_{obs} / 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$	R ²	$k_{obs} / 10^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$

Table SM-3 Retention times, detected peaks in the ESI+ mass spectra, and assignments for degradation products of CIP

Product	Retention time/min	ESI Mode		
		<i>m/z</i>	Attribution (ESI+)	Error/ppm
CIP	8.974	332.1408	[M+H] ⁺	-0.602
		314.1304	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
		288.1507	[M+H-H ₂ O-CO ₂] ⁺	
		245.1081	[M+H-CO ₂ -C ₂ H ₅ N] ⁺	
P1	8.182	306.1258	[M+H] ⁺	1.307
		288.1142	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
P2	9.612	348.1355	[M+H] ⁺	-1.436
		330.1243	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
P3	6.453	334.1198	[M+H] ⁺	-1.496
		316.1039	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
P4	11.425	362.1147	[M+H] ⁺	-1.380
		344.1039	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	
P5	14.052	263.0827	[M+H] ⁺	-1.900
		245.0722	[M+H-H ₂ O] ⁺	

Experimental conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, pH 3.0 and 25 °C.

Table SM-4 Average oxidation state of Mn for MnOOH at distinct conditions: as-prepared (MnOOH) and after 3 h (3-MnOOH) and 6 h (6-MnOOH) of treatment. Experimental conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, pH 3.0, and 25 °C. Mean values were obtained after three repetitions.

Sample	Mn average oxi
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Fig. SM-1 Chemical structure of ciprofloxacin (CIP) antibiotic

Fig. SM-2 X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the as-prepared MnOOH compound.

Fig. SM-3 High-resolution spectrum of C 1s for the as-prepared MnOOH compound.

Fig. SM-4 Evolution of the zeta potential values as a function of the solution pH for the as prepared MnOOH.

An indirect method proposed by Cattania *et al.* [1] and using XPS measurements was also carried out to estimate the pH_{pzc} of the catalyst. In this method, the pH_{pzc} is determined using the chemical shifts of different components in MnOOH together with the linear relationship shown in eq. 1:

$$\text{pH}_{\text{pzc}} = 11.32 - 1.14((\text{BE}_{\text{O}1\text{s oxide}} - 530.0) + (\text{BE}_{\text{cation}} - \text{BE}_{\text{metal}})) \quad (1)$$

where BE is the binding energy of the target component. In this case, $\text{BE}_{\text{cation}} = 642.1$ eV, $\text{BE}_{\text{O}1\text{s oxide}} = 530.8$ eV and, $\text{BE}_{\text{metal}} = 639.0$ eV (value for Mn(s) obtained from [2]). Thus, the pH_{pzc} calculated was 6.9, a value that is in the range reported in the literature for synthetic and mineral MnOOH [3–6].

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Fig. SM-5 Concentration of Mn(II) species leaching from the MnOOH during the reaction at acidic conditions for (■) MnOOH alone, (●) MnOOH/CIP, (▲) MnOOH/PMS, and (▼) MnOOH/CIP/PMS systems. Conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, pH 3.0, and 25 °C.

Fig. SM-6 Remaining fraction of CIP (CIP fraction) and TOC (TOC fraction) as a function of treatment time (t). Effect of homogeneous reactions for oxidation by (Δ) PMS and (\circ) Mn^{2+} /PMS system. Conditions: 50 mg L^{-1} CIP, 350 mg L^{-1} Mn^{2+} , 1.0 g L^{-1} PMS, pH 3.0 and $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Fig. SM-7 Oxidant consumption during the CIP removal using different PMS concentrations: (□) 1.0, (▷) 2.0, and (◉) 4.0 g L⁻¹. Experimental conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, pH 3.0, and 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions.

Fig. SM-8 Total ion chromatographic (TIC) profiles obtained from the separation method developed for CIP in the ESI+ mode at distinct treatment time: **a)** 0 h, **b)** 1 h, **c)** 2 h, **d)** 3 h, **e)** 4 h, **f)** 5 h, and **g)** 6 h.

Fig. SM-9 MS^E acquisition mode for CIP and its degradation products in the ESI+ mode. (a) CIP, (b) P1, (c) P2, (d) P3, (e) P4, and (f) P5. Experimental conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, pH 3.0, and 25 °C.

Fig. SM-10 Concentration evolution of the main detected carboxylic acids as a function of the treatment time (t) during the CIP degradation in the MnOOH/PMS system: (\times) formic, ($+$) acetic, ($*$) propionic, and (\star) adipic acid. Experimental conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, pH 3.0, and 25 °C.

Fig. SM-11 High-resolution spectra of C 1s for MnOOH at distinct conditions: as-prepared (MnOOH) and after 3 h (3-MnOOH) and 6 h (6-MnOOH) of treatment. Experimental conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, pH 3.0, and 25 °C.

Fig. SM-12 X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns for at distinct conditions: as-prepared (MnOOH) and after 6 h (6-MnOOH) of treatment (experimental conditions: 50 mg L⁻¹ CIP, 1.0 g L⁻¹ MnOOH, 1.0 g L⁻¹ PMS, pH 3.0, and 25 °C).

Fig. SM-13 Images of MnOOH powders at distinct conditions: as-prepared (MnOOH), after 3 h (3-MnOOH), and 6 h (6-MnOOH) of treatment.

Fig. SM-14 Cyclic voltammetry (20 mV s^{-1} and 2nd scan) measurements of the as-prepared MnOOH and after 3 (3-MnOOH) and 6 h (6-MnOOH) of treatment. The potential scan started from OCP (open circuit potential – 1 h rest before measurement). The green arrows indicate the scan direction.

Fig. SM-15 a) Complex plane and **b)** Bode plots for the MnOOH samples in the as-prepared condition and after 3 (3-MnOOH) and 6 h (6-MnOOH) of treatment. The equivalent circuit used to fit data generated (see continuous line) by electrochemical impedance is shown in the inset of **a)**.

Fig. SM-16 Time evolution of the charge transfer resistance (R_{oxide}) before and after use of the MnOOH compound to activate PMS. The exposed area was close to 1 cm².

Fig. SM-17 Electron spin resonance measurement for the experiment using MnOOH (1.0 g L^{-1}), PMS (1.0 g L^{-1}), DMPO (100 mol L^{-1}) at pH 3. The spectra named DMPOL (to simulate the alpha hydrogen abstraction), HO^\bullet , and RC^\bullet were simulated and combined (see red line). The carbon radical (RC^\bullet) showed a low intensity signal probably due to the use and manipulation of plastic tips and containers. No signal was observed in the presence of DMPO alone.

Fig. SM-18 Extracted ion chromatogram with identification of DMPO, DMPO-OH (P1) and DMPO(OH)₂ (P2).

Fig. SM-19 MS/MS spectra of **a)** DMPO and its oxidation byproducts **b)** DMPO-OH, and **c)** DMPO-(OH)₂.

Fig. SM-20 Proposed fragmentation route for the DMPO (m/z 114.0913), DMPO-OH (P1: m/z 130.0863), and DMPO-(OH)₂ (P2: m/z 148.0966) compounds.

Fig. SM-21 Electron spin resonance measurement for the experiment using TEMP (black line) and TEMP in the presence of PMS (red line). Conditions: [TEMP] = 50 mmol L⁻¹ and [PMS] = 1.0 g L⁻¹. No significant modifications were observed in the presence of MnOOH.